

Studies on complexes of chalcone with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Mn^{II} metal ions

K. B. Vyas^{a*}, K. S. Nimavat^a, G. R. Jani^b, J. A. Chaudhary^c and M. V. Hathi^{*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Govt. Science College, Gandhinagar-382 015, Gujarat, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, M. N. College, Visnagar-384 315, Gujarat, India

^cR. K. Parikh Arts and Science College, Petlad-388 450, Gujarat, India

E-mail : kirankartik@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 27 April 2009, revised 26 August 2010, accepted 31 August 2010

Abstract : Metal complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Mn^{II} with 3-[[3-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)}-prop-2-enoyl]-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2H-chromene-2-one have been synthesized. These complexes have been characterized using elemental analysis, spectral studies, magnetic susceptibility and molar conductivity measurements. These study reveal that they are having octrahedral geometry of the type ML₂(H₂O)₂ and non-electrolyte in nature. The coordination of the ligand takes place through carbonyl oxygen and phenolic oxygen of the ligand.

Keywords : Chalcone, transition metal complexes, structural studies.

Introduction

Metal complexes are known to play a very important and vital role in biological systems¹. Metal complexes of coumarin derivatives are prepared, characterized and studied spectrophotometrically² and potentiometrically³ by some researchers. The chemistry of chalcone complexes continue to attract many workers because of their wide applicability in various fields⁴⁻⁶.

The present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of metal(II) complexes formed by chalcone of 4-hydroxy-6-methyl coumarin derivative.

Results and discussion

The newly isolated metal complexes are insoluble in acetone, benzene and chloroform. They are freely soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide, dimethyl formamide and 1,4-dioxane. The structure of the metal complexes and the ligand are shown in Scheme. The solids do not melt sharply and undergo decomposition above 290 °C temperature. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis values, which are close with the calculated value.

Molar conductivity measurements :

The conductivity of metal complexes was determined using Thoshniwal Conductivity Bridge. It was dissolved in DMF and conductivity was measured.

Conductivity of the DMF along was measured and solution of the complexes in DMF with different concentration was measured.

The molar conductivity was calculated using the formula.

$$\text{Molecular conductivity} = \frac{1000 \times K}{C}$$

where, *K* = conductivity of the solution of the complexes in DMF, *C* = concentration of the complexes (10⁻³ M). The conductivity data are in Table 1 and the data indicates that the complexes are non-electrolyte in nature⁷.

IR studies :

The FT-IR spectra of all the complexes exhibited a broad peak around 3540-3320 cm⁻¹ and a sharp peak in the range 1623-1617 cm⁻¹. These peaks can be assigned to OH stretching and bending vibration, which indicate the presence of coordinated water molecule in the complexes. The ligand peaks at 1623 and 1626 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=O have been shifted to +15-23 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, which indicate coordination through oxygen atom of the carbonyl group⁸. One new band in the infrared spectrum appears at 560-580 cm⁻¹ which is probably due to M-O band⁹. The peak at 1720 cm⁻¹ is attributed to δ-lactone ring of coumarin. In short, most of the

Table 1. Analytical data of metal(II) complexes

Sr. no.	Molecular formula	m. w.	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Conduc.	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			C	H	Metal		
1.	$\text{Cu}[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6]_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	827.54	60.8 (60.90)	4.5 (4.59)	7.5 (7.67)	7.7	1.74
2.	$\text{Ni}[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6]_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	822.71	61.2 (61.26)	4.5 (4.61)	7.08 (7.13)	9.3	2.82
3.	$\text{Co}[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6]_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	822.93	61.2 (61.24)	4.4 (4.61)	7.0 (7.16)	9.8	3.85
4.	$\text{Mn}[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6]_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	818.93	61.5 (61.54)	4.5 (4.64)	6.5 (6.70)	10.9	5.87

Table 2. Spectral data of metal(II) complexes

Sr. no.	Complexes	Frequencies (cm^{-1})					
		Alkane -CH ₃	Aromatic -CH	Ketone -C=O	Alkene CH=CH	M-O band	Ether C-O-C
4a.	$\text{Cu}[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6]_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	2928, 2834, 1442, 1383	1511, 1249, 832	1650, 1710	1609	590-500	1112
4b.	$\text{Ni}[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6]_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	2920, 2858, 1465, 1384	1562, 1296, 821	1697, 1715	1612	590-500	1130
4c.	$\text{Co}[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6]_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	2922, 2853, 1460, 1375	1554, 1222, 833	1689, 1715	1584	590-500	1138
4d.	$\text{Mn}[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6]_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	2933, 2858, 1464, 1383	1562, 1227, 821	1610, 1732	1602	590-500	1072

Scheme

bands appeared in the spectra of corresponding ligand are observed at the similar position in the IR spectra of metal complexes.

¹H NMR studies :

The ¹H NMR spectra of ligand have been recorded in CDCl₃. In the ligand -OH group appeared at δ 3.91 ppm while -CH₃ proton appeared at δ 2.45 ppm. Two doublets appeared at δ 8.29 and 7.97 ppm due to two ethylenic protons of chalcone. The rest of the protons appeared in the aromatic range at δ 6.5 to 8.0 ppm. An examination of NMR spectra of the ligand reveals that these are on expected lines according to their structures.

Magnetic studies and electronic spectra :

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were obtained at room temperature using Gouy balance. Pure Hg[Co(SCN)₄] was synthesized used as calibration standard¹⁰.

The copper, nickel, cobalt and manganese complexes are paramagnetic in nature. The magnetic moment μ_{eff} values suggest that the complexes have high spin octahedral geometry¹¹.

The UV-Vis spectral data of this ligand and its metal complexes in DMF include absorption regions with band assignments data. The absorption spectrum of the ligand

and metals are characterized mainly by three absorption bands in the region 260–325 nm, which may be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and charge transfer transition, the longer wavelength band is assigned to intra molecular charge transfer, while other due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition within the C=O bonds influenced by charge transfer interaction¹².

The two absorption bands are observed in the region 15600–15885 cm^{-1} and 22225–24697 cm^{-1} , in electronic spectra of Cu^{II} metal complex of the ligand may assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and charge transfer transition respectively¹³. The diffuse reflectance spectra of Ni^{II} coordination compound shown two bands at 15385 and 24394 cm^{-1} assigned to the transitions ${}^3A_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. The electronic spectral data of Co^{II} observed in the range 15625–16650 and around 23000 cm^{-1} may be attributed to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^4T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(P)$ transitions respectively¹⁴. The absorption bands of Mn^{II} complex are found to occur around 16225 cm^{-1} and 24050 cm^{-1} attributed to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ transitions respectively.

From the study of these data it is confirmed that all the complexes possess octahedral geometry.

Experimental

All the reagents were of AR grade and received from BDH, England; Merck, Germany and Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Company, USA. Melting points of the complexes were determined on open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Molar conductance were determined using Toshniwal conductivity bridge on direct reading digital conductivity meter. IR spectra were recorded in the solid state (KBr pellets) in the range 400–4000 cm^{-1} using Shimadzu 435 FT-IR spectrophotometer by KBr technique. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were done using Gouy balance consisting of the type NP-53 electrometer with DC power supply type NP-1053. ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker FT 300 MHz NMR spectrometer in $\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$ solvent using TMS as an internal standard. Elemental analysis was done on Thermofinigan elemental analyzer.

Synthesis of chalcone (ligand)¹⁵ :

A mixture of 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2-benzopyranone (2.52 g, 0.01 M); 3',4'-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (4.15 mL, 0.025 M) and piperidine (1 mL)

were added into ethanol (50 mL). The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for 4 h, cooled and solid was separated. Then it was crystallized from ethanol, reddish yellow coloured compound was obtained (m.w. 362 g, 70%), m.p. 217 °C; ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 2.41 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.85 (2 \times 3H, s, OCH_3), 8.21 (1H, d, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}$), 7.97 (1H, d, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}$), 3.92 (1H, s, $-\text{OH}$), 6.66–7.82 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 68.85; H, 4.91; O, 26.23. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ required for : C, 68.80; H, 4.85; O, 26.15%); IR bands ν_{max} (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1670 (C=O), 1578 (CH=CH), 1031 (C–O–C), 1708 (C=O of δ -lactone ring), 3429 (OH).

Synthesis of metal complexes :

Copper chloride solution (10.0 mL, 0.1 M) diluted to 50 mL and excess of ammonium hydroxide was added to get the pH between 10.5–11.0. It was refluxed with excess of alcoholic solution of 3-[[3-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)]prop-2-enoyl]-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2H-chromen-2-one (3) (3.62 g, 0.1 M) on a water bath for half an hour when light green precipitates of copper complex were obtained. The precipitates were filtered, washed with distilled water and dried at 100 °C. The complex was crystallized from DMF (m.w. 827.54 g, 62%) (Found : C, 60.90; H, 4.59; Cu, 7.67. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6)_2]$ required for : C, 60.80; H, 4.45; Cu, 7.50%); IR bands ν_{max} (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1619 (C=O), 1587 (CH=CH), 1072 (C–O–C), 1732 (C=O of δ -lactone ring), 590–500 (Cu–O).

Similarly other metal complexes were prepared. The complexes did not show clear melting point. They charred at temperature above 290 °C.

Conclusion :

The structural study of these M^{II} complexes reveals that all complexes are paramagnetic in nature and having octahedral geometry. The ligand can be used as an analytical reagent for some metal ions. The synthesized metal complexes may also have some biological activities.

References

1. S. U. Rehman, Z. H. Chohan, G. Farzana and C. T. Supuran, *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry*, 2005, 20, 333.
2. S. M. Dave, K. L. Dubal, V. R. Ram, A. H. Bapodra and H. S. Joshi, *PRAJNA-Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 2009, 17, 68.
3. K. B. Vyas, K. S. Nimavat, G. R. Jani, R. P. Patel, J. A.

- Chaudhary and M. V. Hathi, *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 2010, **1**, 12.
4. S. Baluja, N. Kachhadia and R. Bhalodiya, *Journal of the Institute of Chemists, India*, 2007, **79**, 17.
 5. Magdalena Grazul and Elzbieta Budzisz, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **253**, 21.
 6. K. B. Vyas, G. R. Jani and M. V. Hathi, *E-Journal of Chemistry*, 2009, **6**, 1121.
 7. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 82.
 8. N. B. Colthup, *J. Optical Soc. Am.*, 1950, **40**, 307.
 9. M. Thirumalai, Kumar and S. Sivakolunthy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 7250.
 10. B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **5**, 210.
 11. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience, 1962.
 12. L. Larabi, Y. Harek, A. Regiug and M. M. Nostafa, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **68**, 85.
 13. V. M. Ellis, R. S. Vagg and E. C. Watton, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1031.
 14. J. Lewis and R. S. Wilkins, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", New York, 1960, p. 290.
 15. P. L. Cheng, Fournari and Tirouflet, *J. Bull. Soc. Chem. France*, 1963, 102248 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, **60**, 1683).